

AKMEOLOGICAL TRAINING FOR COORDINATING THE PROFESSIONAL SKILLS DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15271286>

Abstract. *Creative technologies for developing the professional skills of future primary school teachers based on an acmeological approach are currently being applied in global education systems. The development of professional competence in future specialists through the acmeological approach involves systematic work in improving students' social competencies, identifying the didactic potential of acme-technologies, and forming technologies that influence professional mastery. In this article, as part of implementing the acmeological approach, the acmeological orientation of the individual, the conditions of the organizational environment, and the characteristics of institutions where the acmeological approach is applied are considered. During the research, we examined the conditions that determine the possibility and success of implementing the acmeological approach.*

Keywords: *Acmeological approach, professional competence, acmeological research, pedagogical mechanism, educational acmeology, value, professional orientation, acmeological guidance, professional pedagogical education, acmeological principles, integrated approach.*

Professionally significant success, which has social and objective importance, refers to a high level of individual professional achievements, significantly exceeding the normative level recognized as a socially acceptable result by the professional community. Such outcomes usually indicate a person's high level of professional mastery and transition beyond it.

The result of students' pedagogical training based on the acmeological approach is the formation of their acmeological orientation, which is considered a new indicator of higher education quality. It should be understood as an integral part of preparation, enabling the mature specialist to progressively advance in their profession by increasingly tackling complex tasks and fully utilizing the psychological resources available to humans. This interrelation yields effective outcomes in continuous professional development.

As of today, there is no clear definition of the phenomenon of applying the acmeological approach in the training of future specialists, nor is there a deep understanding of its structure and essential content. The ambiguous interpretations of the subject of acmeology—from narrow-specialist to broad-activity domains—are related to the complexity of the core concepts of personal attention. The influence of acmeological factors during the student's personal and professional development determines the following aspects of personal orientation: professional interests and needs, motivation for success, the need for self-awareness and self-development, and students' creativity. A.A.Derkach emphasized that all these factors contribute to clarifying the content of students' acmeological orientation.

By defining the content of students' acmeological orientation, we highlight its leading function—defining and updating a person's creative activity aimed at self-improvement and achieving the highest levels of personality development. In any activity, the specific professional-pedagogical

content of acmeological orientation implies that future primary school teachers are guided towards implementing it in their professional work. The concept of acmeological education, along with the theoretical and methodological foundations of acmeological teaching, suggests the importance of forming students' acmeological orientation in detail.

According to the structure we have defined, we consider students' acmeological orientation as a combination of four components: goal-forming, value-oriented, motivational-content-based, and productive. Their essence is described throughout this process.

As S.N.Begidova emphasized, emotional and value-based attitude toward an activity is an integral component that ensures the success of its implementation [8].

During the research confirmed by L.Khabayeva's studies, the author identified a strong correlation—the correlation coefficient between the value-oriented professional activity formed by students and the effectiveness of their professional self-awareness was found to be 0.88.

Values themselves are objective, as they are formed in the process of socio-historical practice; their significance for students depends on the subjective attitude towards them — thus becoming values. Therefore, assessing students may be incorrect if it does not correspond to the actual value.

V.V.Serikov argues that the highest human values must be reinterpreted through students' experiences; otherwise, they will not be able to assimilate them adequately, and such values will not have personal meaning for them.

For this reason, S.N.Begidova believes it is necessary to develop in individuals an attitude toward accepting objective values and internalizing social norms [8].

F.I.Bliyeva states that during the process of entering a profession, a person develops a professional value orientation, and the social values of the profession are subject to subjective and individual reflection in the psyche and consciousness of the specialist [13].

This method, based on the goal and objectives of identifying the motivational and value structure of an individual, was named the **“Morphological Test of Life Values” (MTLV)**.

The main diagnostic construct of the MTLV is terminal values. The term "value" refers to the subject's attitude toward an event, life fact, object or subject, and the recognition of its importance and vital significance.

The list of life values includes the following:

1. Self-development – recognizing one's personal traits and continuously developing one's abilities and other individual characteristics.
2. Spiritual fulfillment – being guided by moral principles and prioritizing spiritual needs over material ones.
3. Creativity – realizing one's creative potential and the desire to transform surrounding reality.
4. Active social relationships – establishing favorable relationships in various areas of social interaction, expanding interpersonal communication, and fulfilling one's social role.
5. Personal prestige – gaining recognition in society by adhering to certain social standards.
6. High financial status – emphasizing material well-being as a fundamental aspect of existence.
7. Achievement of success – setting and solving specific life challenges as key life priorities.

8. Preservation of individuality – maintaining and defending one’s uniqueness, independence, and personal beliefs even if they differ from commonly accepted ones.

1-table. Technology for Developing the Professional Competence of Future Primary School Teachers Based on an Acmeological Approach

Block 1. Attitude Toward Professional Activity	1. Methodology: "The Actual and Potential Meanings and Values of a Professional"
Block 2. Attitude Toward Innovation	2. Reflective Workshop
Block 3. Motivation for Achieving Success	3.Seminar on "Managing Yourself and Your Time"

The first stage involves diagnosing the level of acmeological approach of future primary school teachers (before and after the implementation of the technology). The outcome indicating the effectiveness of the implemented technology is the dynamics of the acmeological approach in the process of professional training (an increase in the level of acmeological approach).

The second stage (practical) includes the development of an acmeological approach among future primary school teachers, which consists of the following methods:

1. "Real and Potential Meanings and Values of Pedagogical Activity".

The aim of this methodology is to help the teacher understand both the general meanings and values of pedagogical activity and the specific meanings and values of their own professional work.

2. "Reflective" training.

The "Reflective" training addresses the psychological content of the phenomenon of reflection: its mechanisms, and its role and significance in the consciousness and activity of a future primary school teacher. It also focuses on ways and methods to develop the reflective ability of future primary school teachers.

Objective: To develop the reflective ability of future primary school teacher participants.

This objective is achieved through the following tasks:

- Encouraging participants to reflect on the motives that led them to pursue the teaching profession in the future;

- Promoting reflection and understanding of general and personal professional beliefs of future primary school teachers;

- Encouraging participants to describe themselves as professionals;

- Exploring metaphors related to the roles of student and teacher, and forming a clear vision of general educational tasks in the consciousness of future primary school teachers;

- Pedagogical reflection on complex professional situations in interactions with students, parents, colleagues, and administration.

All tasks are carried out through active learning methods: conducting exercises, tests, interviews, completing creative assignments, using game-based techniques and case methods. At the end of each session, a discussion (reflection) is held.

3. "Self and Time Management" Training.

This consists of two parts:

- Self-management, which involves mastering and applying effective ways to organize one's activities, considering personal resources—aimed at future primary school teachers;
- Time management, which focuses on acquiring techniques for optimal time use.

4. "Motivational" Training.

This training involves discussing methods and techniques for stimulating and managing motivation. Examples of motivation and self-motivation are provided, and motivational diagnostics are conducted.

5. Training on Updating Acmeological Potential is based on the first group of acmeological technologies—"Game Technologies"—which include the following:

- Business games, which serve as a way to reconstruct thematic and social content and model systems of relationships typical of professional activities and, in general, the activity of future primary school teachers;

- Didactic games, which are characterized by the absence of a single solution path, and the fulfillment of developmental tasks, activating participants to independently seek solutions;

- Situation analysis and game design are also employed.

6. "Self-Care" Psychological Marathon.

Within this psychological marathon, the following questions are raised:

- How do I need to change myself?
- How should I care for myself?
- What changes must I make in my personality to become a modern person and professional capable of achieving the goals I set?
- If my profession involves caring for others, do I know how to take care of myself?

The psychological marathon is carried out using existential-acmeological game technologies, musical accompaniment, discussions, experience sharing, reflection, and the drawing technique.

7. "Individual Acmeological Professional Trajectory" Training.

The aim of this training is to construct an individual professional acmeological trajectory (an individual development plan for personal and professional growth) based on the following structure:

A. Participants are asked to individually answer the following questions based on the analysis of the meanings and values of their future professional activities:

- What do I see as the meaning of my professional activity?
- What are my professional achievements so far?
- What prospects do I see for my professional development (in 5, 10, 15 years)?
- What priorities do I set for myself?
- What stages do I identify in my professional development?
- What professional goals do I set for myself?
- Do my professional goals align with my non-professional goals (personal, family, leisure, etc.)?
- What factors (heredity, environment, activity, conditions) may influence my plans?
- What professional achievements do I want to attain in the future?
- What actions do I plan to take for my future professional development?

B. Discussion in groups of 3–4 participants.

C. General group discussion:

Question: What new insights about your professional development (goals, priorities, potential achievements) did you gain during the construction of your professional acmeological trajectory?

D. Developing a personal and professional development plan (individually).

Analysis of Scientific Sources on Developing Professional Skills of Students Based on the Akmeological Approach:

- The theoretical analysis of the necessary conditions for the development of professional skills of university students based on the akmeological approach includes studying the problems of identifying and understanding the role of akmeoperson (ideal professional characteristics) within the structure of virtues.

- The methods for facilitating management, viewed as an akmeshaxs in social sectors, were identified in the context of pedagogical akmeology and include approaches for simplifying management in response to social demand.

- The development of professional skills of students based on the akmeological approach was noted as a factor for increasing the social sustainability of society and its sustainable development.

- The akmeological approach prepares students for successful professional activity, which, in turn, defines the elements of the academic disciplines such as “pedagogical akmeology,” “general pedagogy,” and “pedagogical skills” in higher educational institutions.

- It was emphasized that today the akmeological approach is considered a priority, and its pedagogical aspects are crucial in preparing students with practical social knowledge that can be applied in solving a wide range of real-life tasks.

- The development of professional skills was explained as the totality of students' obligations, which enables them to responsibly and effectively apply their knowledge and skills in practice.

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